

RESEARCH ARTICLE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY – MEMORY OF *VATA PRADHANA PRAKRITI* AND *KAPHA PRADHANA PRAKRITI* INDIVIDUALS - A PILOT STUDY

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Abstract:

Prakriti is the Sanskrit word for a person's inherent qualities. According to Ayurveda, prakriti refers to a person's mental and physical build. Smriti derives its name from the verb smr, which means "to remember" in Sanskrit [1]. The study's goal was to evaluate state of *Smriti* (memory) in various *Prakruti* (phenotype). The study was conduct on the students of Parul Institute of Ayurved, Limda, Waghodia, Vadodara, Gujrat, India with the age group of 18-30. Volunteers was selected randomly and then grouped into *Vata Pradhana* and *Kapha Pradhana Prakriti*. *Prakriti* was assessed by software and memory was assessed by ACE scale. The findings demonstrate a strong relationship between *Prakruti* and *Smriti*. As memory test done under different domains like- attention, memory, verbal fluency, language and visuospatial abilities: all were found corelation with *Prakriti*. *Kapha Pradhana* comparing *Prakruti* to *Vata Pradhana*, performed better on most of the examinations.

Key words: *Prakriti, Kapha Pradhana, Vata Pradhana, ACE scale, Memory.*

Introduction:

Prakriti is said to be influenced by maternal variables such as the mother's diet, lifestyle choices, and intrauterine environment (*Matru Ahara Vihara*). The fundamental nature of an individual, which is established at the time of fertilization, typically doesn't change over the course of their lifetime. *Prakriti* is formed at the time of sperm-ovum union in accordance to attributes of predominant Dosha. This Dosha predominance is in normal state and not an aggravated According to *Dalhana*, these predominant *Vata* etc. are of two types Normal and Abnormal of which the former emerging simultaneously with the body are source of natural constitution while the latter cause abnormality in foetus [3].

Gayadas interprets this in somewhat different way he says that if the entire seed is vitiated the embryo would not come forth but when a portion of the same is vitiated by Dosha some abnormal features appear in comparison to the healthy one such as cracks in palm, soles etc [3]. The review explored the concept of *Manasik Prakriti* impersonate in the Ayurvedic literature. It shows Satva quality is responsible for the mental goodness and health while Rajas and Tamas take the authority of various mental frustration.[21] The pre-assessment of *Manasik Prakriti* can be useful for determining the status of the three parts and the mental state of a certain person,

which can aid in determining the severity of illnesses, adjusting medication dosages, and organising customised psychotherapy.

Because of the correlation between *Manas* and *Deha*, specific counselling, drug kind, dose, and don'ts can be suggested for rapid improvement. Learning could not occur without the function of memory. [22] So-called intelligent behaviour demands memory, remembering being prerequisite to reasoning. The ability to solve any problem or even to recognize that a problem exists depends on memory. [20]

The only thing that counts as memory is the recall of previously directly viewed, heard, or experienced events. It is listed as one of the eight desires for power, and achieving it requires attention. One of the brain's most intricate functions is memory. It is stated that *Aatma* (the soul), *Mana*, *Buddhi*, and *Medha* work together to create memory (Retentive Faculty of memory).

According to the literature, people who have *Vata Prakriti* have good grasping power, short memories, an unstable mind, and poor memories. Regulation of Vata Dosha leads to overall better status of body performance, as functions of all the organs, including vital organs, are controlled by Vata [23] They are Quick to remember and forgets quickly with less accuracy. The primary dosha that regulates the mind's normal operations and functioning is *Vata*. *Udana Vayu* is the primary dosha engaged in the process of achieving smriti. The other sort of dosha that affects memory processing is *Prana Vata*, which keeps *buddhi*, *mana*, and *Indriya* functioning properly.

Shruta grahino alpasmritayah (cha. Vi. 8/108), *chala dhriti smriti buddhi (A.H. sha.3/86)*, *na dridha na jitendriya (A.H. sha.3/87)*. Thus, as per text, *Vata Prakriti* individual have poor memory, unstable mind and short memories.

The ancient *Acharyas* described the *Kapha Prakriti* people as being blessed with education, being of steady mind, having strong textual knowledge, having a good memory, and being intelligent. This shows that the *Kapha Prakriti* are the most intelligent, highly skilled, and memory rich. They are slow to remember and forgets slowly with more accuracy. When it comes to memory function, *Prana Vayu*, *Udana Vayu*, *Sadhaka Pitta*, and *Tarpaka Kapha* all work together.

Smritimaana, dhriti maana (A. H. sha. 3/99) [7], *Vidhyavanta, Ojaswina (cha.vi.8/96)* [8], *Kritaghno Dhritimaana Sahishnu (su. sha. 4/71)* [9] these are some terminologies used to describe characteristics related to memory. The personality of those who are predominantly *Kapha* are calm, steady, stable, and patient. Long memory and repetition are the keys of learning.

There is a rising need in today's culture for Ayurveda science to comprehend the complexity of *Ayurvedic* principles on the basis of contemporary medical science in an understandable way. Modern criteria must therefore be used to evaluate memory. A strong memory will enhance social skills, career prospects, educational standards, and life comprehension. So, understanding how prakriti and memory are related will be helpful in the aforementioned domains [13].

Materials and method:

Participants:

Volunteers were screened for *Vata* and *Kapha Pradhana* prakriti first and then included in study. Total 43 participants were screened. Among them, 19 were found *Vata Pradhana* and

18 were *Kapha Pradhana Prakriti*. From both *Vata* and *Kapha Pradhana Prakriti*, 15 each volunteer is selected. Sample size (N= 30) was chosen for data analysis and observation. Before to participation, participants gave their written consent with complete transparency.

Objectives:

To assess *Vata Pradhana prakriti*.

To assess *Kapha Pradhana prakriti*.

To assess memory. (ACE Scale)

To compare memory of *Vata* and *Kapha pradhana prakriti* individuals.

Materials:

Ayu soft: The programme Ayu Soft, a decision support system, was created by the Centre for Development of Advanced Computing (CDAC) in Pune, India. It will make ayurveda research, diagnosis, and treatment easier for practitioners, hospitals, and researchers [19].

By this, the Prakriti assessment was done. Then, memory assessment was done by ACE Scale.

ACE scale: The Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination-III is the most recent version of the examination (ACE-III). These 19 exercises assess the following five cognitive functions: language, fluency, attention, visuospatial abilities and memory [12].

Procedure:

All the participants are screened individually. First informed written consent was taken. Then health assessment was done to rule out healthy status. Case record form containing their personal information was filled by them. Then prakriti examination was done by Ayu soft software. The Prakriti result arrived in the form of Anatomical, Physiological, Phycological and total score. only total score is considered and then Prakriti was decided. After that, memory assessment was done by ACE Scale. 5 domains were assessed and from total 100 the points were counted. Then co-relation of score of ACE Scale was done among the participants of *Vata Pradhana Prakriti* and *Kapha Pradhana Prakriti*.

OBSERVATION:

Here, is the memory score of both Prakriti individuals.

Table 1: memory of *Vata Pradhana Prakriti* and *Kapha Pradhana Prakriti*

Memory score of <i>Vata Prakriti</i>	Memory score of <i>Kapha Prakriti</i>
72	76
46	77
69	77
66	78
72	75
75	68
73	73
59	79
62	79
70	73
69	79
67	78
70	74

73	74
72	78

Result:

Participants score on the ACE scale and Ayu soft and their Prakriti and Memory Score found and co relation between them are summarized in table given above. As expected, we found the memory of *Vata pradhana prakriti* is lower than *Kapha Pradhana Prakriti*. Mean of variable 1 which is of *Vata Pradhana Prakriti* person is 67.66 and variable 2 which is of *Kapha Pradhana Prakriti* person is 75.86.

Value of P(T<=t) one-tail is 0.0004 which is lesser than 0.05. it indicated that the result is significant. P<0.05. This analysis confirms that the significance level. Thus, outcome of this study is as expected. (*Vata pradhana prakriti* has less memory than *Kapha Pradhana Prakriti*)

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	67.66666667	75.86666667

Variance	54.38095238	9.40952381
Observations	15	15
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	19	
t Stat	-3.97632213	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.000404387	
t Critical one-tail	1.729132812	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.000808775	
t Critical two-tail	2.093024054	

Table 2: result

Discussion:

Memory' labels a diverse set of cognitive capacities by which information is retained and reconstruct past experiences, usually for present purposes. Memory is one of the most important ways by which our histories animate our current actions and experiences. Memory seems to be a source of knowledge. Etymologically, the word 'memory' comes from the Middle English memory, which in turn comes from the Anglo-French memoire or memories, and ultimately from the Latin word Memoria and memory, meaning "mindful" or "remembering" [2]. There are 5 domains in the memory scale: language, fluency, attention, visuospatial abilities and memory. Among them, attention and fluency domains are seen good in the *Vata pradhana prakriti* due to their good grasping power (*Shrutagrahino*) but other domains like memory, visuospatial and language are not that much good because of their *Chala* and *Laghu guna*. According to A.H., they have also *Alpa Smriti* and *Alpa Dhriti*. That is why the memory of *Vata pradhana prakriti* is low.

In case of *Kapha Pradhana Prakriti*, due to *Sthira* and *Manda guna* and *Dharana Karma*; the memory of them is stable and good. According to A.H. they have *Dirgha smriti*, *Smritimana* and *Dhritimana*. According to *Charakacharya*, they are *Vidyavanta* and *Ojaswina* [11]. *Kapha* dosha is having dominance of Prithvi and *Jala Mahabhuta* Which provide stability to body and mind. Thus, in this *Prakriti*, memory, visuospatial and attention are better than the *Vata Pradhana Prakriti* person.

Buddhi, Hruday and chit Druk are the Function of *Prana* which resides in Shira sthana. Shira is also the *sthana* of *Tarpaka Kapha*. *Tarpaka Kapha* provides nourishment to the Brain and Indriya [14]. In other way we can say for proper functioning of *Prana Vayu* Nourishment by *Tarpaka Kapha* is needed.

Smriti is a kind of perception derived from a person's impressions of past events. If a person is having the identical experience for the first time due to an external environment. *Anubhavjanya Gyana* i.e., the same knowledge is called *Smriti* when it is digested, retained, and replicated [10].

REFERANCES:

1. Available from: [What is Smriti? - Definition from Yogapedia](#)

2. “A STUDY TO EVALUATE EFFECT OF DHYANA ON CONCENTRATION AND SHORT-TERM MEMORY OF COLLEGE GOING STUDENTS” by Dr. Jitendra Sharma, Dr. Vaidehi Raole.
3. “A STUDY TO EVALUATE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIFFERENT PRAKRITI AND SHUKRA SARA PURUSH W.S.R. TO SEMEN ANALYSIS” by Dr. Abhishek N. Acharya, Dr. Sunil Nikhate, Dr. Deepika Chaudhari. (PDF) Relationship between Shukra Sara Purusha with Quality of Semen: A Pilot Study (researchgate.net)
4. A conceptual study on Medha, Buddhi, Dhee, Dhruti, Smruti and Manas Dr. Sujit Kumar, Dr. Deepika Mehra, Dr. Vaidehi V Raole and Dr. Sunil P Nikhate. (PDF) The conceptual Study on Buddhi, Dhee, Dhruti, Smruti, and Manas (researchgate.net)
5. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Dipika Commentary by Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamji Acharya, Varanasi, Choukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, Reprinted 2005.
6. Dr. Nandini dhargalkar, Sharira Kriya Vigyana, Charaka Samhita Vimaan Sthana chapter no.8 verses no. 97
7. Asthang Hridaya, sharira sthana, chauhambha Sanskrit samsthna: chapter no.3 verses 99.
8. Dr. Nandini dhargalkar, sharira kriya vigyana , charaka Samhita sharira sthana 8 verse 96, pg.no. 190.
9. Prof. Rajendra Deshpande Prof. Shivajirav, Sushruta Samhita sharira sthana chapter no. 4 verse 71. pg.no.259.
10. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331087743>
11. Available from: <http://ijapr.in>
12. Available from: Validation of the Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination III in Frontotemporal Dementia and Alzheimer's Disease - Abstract - Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders 2013, Vol. 36, No. 3-4 - Karger Publishers
13. Mindfulness Meditation Improves Visual Short-Term Memory Molly A. Youngs, Samuel E. Lee, and Michael O. Mireku School of Psychology, University of Lincoln, Lincoln, UK Dinkar Sharma School of Psychology, University of Kent, Canterbury, UK Robin S. S. Kramer School of Psychology, University of Lincoln, Lincoln, UK.
14. Available from: What Is Long-Term Memory? Types, Duration, Capacity (verywellmind.com)
15. Acharya YT, Acharya NR. Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta. 7th ed., Varanasi: Chowkamba orientalia, 2003.
16. Anna Moreshwar Kunte. Ashtanga hrudaya of Vagbhata. 7th Ed, Varanasi: Chowkamba Samskrit Adhishtan, 2002.
17. Vaidya Tarachanda Sharma, Ayurvediya Padartha Vijnana, 9th Ed, Rohataka, Nath Pustaka Bhandara Publishers, 1994.
18. (PDF) STATUS OF DRISHTA SMRITI (VISUAL MEMORY) AND SHRUTA SMRITI (AUDITORY MEMORY) IN DIFFERENT PRAKRUTI: A QUESTIONNAIRE BASED SURVEY STUDY (researchgate.net)
19. Available from: [ayusoft cdac - Search \(bing.com\)](https://www.ayusoft.com/cdac)
20. Available from: Memory | Definition, Retrieval, & Forgetting | Britannica

21. PHYSIOLOGICAL STUDY OF MANASIK PRAKRITI W.S.R TO PSYCHOSOMATIC DISORDER Amit Mehra¹ , Gugulothu Ramesh² , Raghvendra Mishra³ , Divyang Dev Goswami⁴
22. A Review on Assessment of Manas Prakriti Dr. S. S. Sant¹ , Vd. Sanjivani Tukaram Hambarde
23. AN UNDERSTANDING TOWARDS THE MODE OF ACTION OF BENEFITS OF MANTRA CHANTING Kulkarni Akshar Ashok ^{1*}, Joshi Abhijit H ², Gadgil Neha D ¹ IPh D Scholar, Tilak Maharashtra Vidyapeeth, Pune & Assistant Professor, SDM College of Ayurveda & Hospital, Hassan, Karnataka, India ²Guide and Head, Department of Ayurved, Tilak Maharashtra Vidyapeeth, Pune, Maharashtra, India [AN-UNDERSTANDING-TOWARDS-THE-MODE-OF-ACTION-OF-BENEFITS-OF-MANTRA-CHANTING.pdf \(researchgate.net\)](#)